

Speed of sound and associated acoustical parameters of Schiff base solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K

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Abstract : The density, viscosity and speed of sound (2 MHz) in chloroform and DMF solutions of 2- and 4-hydroxy Schiff bases were investigated at 303, 308 and 313 K. Using speed of sound, viscosity and density data of Schiff base solutions various acoustical parameters such as specific acoustical impedance (Z), adiabatic compressibility (κ_a), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f), intermolecular free path length (L_f), classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_c$), and viscous relaxation time (τ) were determined and correlated with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature. A fairly good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration of Schiff bases was observed. Linear or non-linear increase or decrease of studied acoustical parameters with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature indicated existence of strong molecular interactions. The linear or non-linear increase of S_n with concentration of Schiff bases and decrease with temperature further supported the existence of strong molecular interactions.

Keywords : Schiff base, speed of sound, density, viscosity, acoustical parameters, solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions.

Introduction

Ultrasonic technology is used in various fields in investigating compatibility of polymer blends to achieve mechanical integrity, better adhesion and better processing^{1,2}. The thermo-acoustic properties is of great significance in studying the physico-chemical behavior and molecular arrangement in various liquid mixtures^{3,4}, while the speed of sound and related acoustical parameters provide information about molecular interactions, the nature and strength of interactions⁵⁻⁸, chemical interactions e.g. ionic or covalent, charge-transfer, hydrogen bonding, ionic-dipole interaction, hydrophilic interaction^{9,10}. Solvation number is a powerful tool in determining the strength of the molecular interactions in the solutions. It provides information about structure making or structure breaking tendency of the solutes under study.

The Schiff bases find their industrial importance as fine chemicals, ligands for metal complexes and drug intermediates¹¹⁻¹⁴. Various interactions such as ionic or covalent, charge transfer, H-bonding, ionic-dipole, hydrophilic, solvent-solute interactions affect the physiologi-

cal action of the drugs^{15,16}. Speed of sound, viscosity, diffusion, and thermal conductivity¹²⁻¹⁵ are important tools in understanding transport of drugs across biological membranes. With a view to understand molecular interactions in symmetric double Schiff base solutions here with we have reported density, viscosity and speed of sound of Schiff bases (**1**) solutions of 1,1'-bis(4-aminophenyl)cyclohexane and 2-hydroxy and 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde at three different temperatures and derived various acoustical parameters.

SDSB-1 : R = 2-OH

SDSB-2 : R = 4-OH

Experimental

Reagents and techniques :

Chloroform (CF) and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF)

used in the present study were of laboratory grade and purified according to literature methods¹⁷. Schiff bases SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 were synthesized and crystallized according to our previous work¹⁸. SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 are only soluble in CF and DMF and therefore these solvents are selected to understand characteristic molecular interactions in the solutions. A 0.1 mol stock Schiff bases solutions were prepared and from them a series of dilute solutions were prepared at room temperature.

Measurements :

The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) measurements of CF, DMF and Schiff bases solutions were carried out at 303, 308 and 313 K by using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi) Model No. F-81, operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U measurements were accurate to $\pm 0.1 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, 0.01 mPa s and $\pm 0.15\%$, respectively. The accuracies of the measurements were determined by pooled precision standard deviations.

Results and discussion

The ρ , η and U data of CF, DMF, SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K are reported in Tables

1 and 2, respectively. The ρ , η and U data were correlated with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature. The least square equations along with correlation coefficients are reported in Tables 3 and 4. The ρ is decreased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature in CF system, while it is increased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and decreased linearly with temperature in DMF system. CF is denser than those of Schiff bases, while DMF is lighter than those of Schiff bases and therefore ρ decreased in CF system and increased in DMF system in accordance to law of additivity. Viscosity is increased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and is decreased with temperature in both the systems studied. Speed of sound is increased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and decreased linearly with temperature in CF, while it is increased with temperature in DMF system decrease in cohesive forces. Various types of molecular interactions in the solutions affect the overall values of the density, viscosity and speed of sound. Molecular association leads to change in apparent molecular mass and volume and hence density of the solutions. Thus, cohesive forces play an important role in determining ultimate properties of the solutions. From Tables 1 and 2, it is clear that a good to excellent correla-

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) data of SDSB-1 solutions at three different temperatures

Conc. (mol/ dm ³)	Density ρ (kg m ⁻³)			Viscosity $\eta \times 10^3$ (mPa s)			U (m s ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
	SDSB-1 + CF								
0	1465.7	1460.9	1457.3	0.619	0.574	0.554	959.0	945.4	924.6
0.01	1460.6	1455.0	1454.8	0.646	0.584	0.562	963.0	949.2	936.8
0.02	1456.4	1451.0	1446.3	0.671	0.617	0.597	967.4	953.6	943.4
0.04	1452.8	1447.7	1442.0	0.717	0.655	0.648	972.4	959.0	950.6
0.06	1447.3	1443.8	1438.2	0.739	0.696	0.671	978.6	965.2	956.8
0.08	1443.0	1440.2	1435.3	0.776	0.738	0.705	985.0	969.2	961.2
0.10	1440.6	1437.0	1432.7	0.814	0.766	0.736	991.4	973.6	965.2
	SDSB-1 + DMF								
0	932.8	927.5	916.4	0.848	0.815	0.777	1451.4	1458.6	1464.4
0.01	944.8	944.3	943.1	0.926	0.892	0.830	1459.2	1463.8	1465.6
0.02	946.5	945.5	945.1	0.959	0.920	0.893	1469.6	1471.2	1475.2
0.04	948.9	947.7	947.0	0.982	0.944	0.927	1477.2	1479.8	1484.8
0.06	950.6	949.4	947.7	0.997	0.959	0.950	1487.2	1491.2	1499.6
0.08	953.6	951.0	950.4	1.029	0.988	0.981	1495.0	1499.0	1509.2
0.10	956.0	953.1	952.5	1.051	1.013	0.996	1501.4	1507.6	1513.0

Table 2. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) data of SDSB-2 solutions at three different temperatures

Conc. (mol/ dm ³)	Density ρ (kg m ⁻³)			Viscosity $\eta \times 10^3$ (mPa s)			U (m s ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
SDSB-2 + CF									
0	1465.7	1460.9	1457.3	0.620	0.574	0.554	959.0	945.4	924.6
0.01	1458.4	1454.9	1453.6	0.636	0.629	0.590	960.2	946.8	928.8
0.02	1454.3	1452.4	1450.9	0.700	0.655	0.625	965.4	949.0	933.6
0.04	1449.8	1448.5	1447.3	0.721	0.683	0.661	973.2	951.4	937.2
0.06	1446.2	1445.1	1443.9	0.760	0.717	0.694	979.4	955.6	941.0
0.08	1442.9	1442.0	1440.8	0.773	0.750	0.725	985.0	957.2	944.2
0.10	1441.2	1439.6	1438.4	0.809	0.774	0.750	989.6	959.2	947.6
SDSB-2 + DMF									
0	932.8	927.5	916.4	0.848	0.815	0.777	1451.4	1458.6	1464.4
0.01	945.8	944.5	943.9	0.896	0.855	0.828	1455.2	1463.6	1468.6
0.02	947.2	946.1	946.0	0.937	0.885	0.852	1461.4	1469.2	1475.4
0.04	949.4	948.5	947.6	0.962	0.925	0.899	1467.0	1476.4	1483.2
0.06	951.2	950.7	950.4	0.999	0.946	0.931	1477.6	1483.2	1489.4
0.08	954.4	953.5	953.1	1.038	1.005	0.967	1485.2	1491.4	1495.2
0.10	956.5	955.6	955.4	1.066	1.025	0.999	1491.2	1497.2	1501.2

Table 3. The least square fitted values of the parameters of different equations (C is the concentration) and correlation coefficients for SDSB-1

Parameter	Least square equations (Correlation coefficients, γ)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K
SDSB-1 + CF			
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1461.6 – 222.27C (-0.990)	1455.7 – 192.47C (-0.994)	1455.7 – 165.56C (0.995)
η (mPa s)	0.634 + 1.798C (0.996)	0.5742 + 2.006C (0.996)	0.558 + 1.841C (0.987)
U (m s ⁻¹)	960.36 + 308.55C (0.999)	947.83 + 267.23C (0.995)	936.53 + 305.86C (0.984)
$\kappa_a \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	7.415 – 3.453C (-0.999)	7.644 – 3.161C (-0.993)	7.867 – 4.052C (-0.991)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (M)	5.702 – 1.367C (-0.995)	5.787 – 1.208C (-0.996)	5877 – 1.586C (-0.974)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	4.052 + 5.714C – 119.64C ² + 650.99C ³ (0.931)	3.957 + 3.618C – 35.978C ² + 93.394C ³ (0.954)	3.891 + 10.995C – 191.02C ² + 962.95C ³ (0.966)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	2.72 – 4.587C (-0.973)	3.089 – 7.207C (-0.978)	3.168 – 6.766C (-0.945)
SDSB-1 + DMF			
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	943.8 + 121.21C (0.998)	943.57 + 95.342C (0.998)	942.62 + 97.096C (0.988)
η (mPa s)	0.924 + 1.293C (0.986)	0.888 + 1.255C (0.991)	0.84 + 1.631C (0.942)
U (m s ⁻¹)	1458.3 + 451.73C (0.989)	1460.6 + 480.27C (0.997)	1463.4 + 539.45C (0.986)

Table-3 (contd.)

$\kappa_a \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	4.98 – 3.540C (-0.991)	4.96 – 3.567C (-0.997)	4.95 – 3.922C (-0.988)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	4.642 – 1.260C (-0.967)	4.66 – 1.622C (-0.996)	4.66 – 1.91C (-0.993)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	5.282 – 10.328C (-0.998)	5.258 – 10.397C (-0.998)	5.2 – 9.279C (-0.993)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	1.404 + 3.255C (0.992)	1.493 + 3.4934C (0.993)	1.548 + 3.43C (0.996)

Table 4. The least square fitted values of the parameters of different equations (C is concentration) and correlation coefficients for SDSB-2

Parameter	Least square equations (Correlation coefficients, γ)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K
	SDSB-2 + CF		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1458.5 – 187.73C (-0.981)	1455.9 – 169.78C (-0.995)	1454.5 – 167.53C (-0.995)
η (mPa s)	0.646 + 1.685C (0.961)	0.615 + 1.597C (0.997)	0.585 + 1.724C (0.991)
U (m s ⁻¹)	958.76 + 323.4C (0.993)	946.03 + 138.74C (0.989)	928.57 + 196.71C (0.988)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	7.456 – 3.868C (-0.993)	7.674 – 1.317C (-0.981)	7.972 – 2.384C (-0.982)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	5.721 – 1.598C (-0.991)	5.803 – 0.549C (-0.994)	5.913 – 0.923C (-0.982)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	3.948 + 17.614C – 382.55 C2 + 2287.9C ³ (0.836)	4.107 + 4.3904C – 108.59C ² + 733.61C ³ (0.788)	4.035 + 9.581C – 192.41C ² + 1152.7C ³ (0.971)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	2.506 – 2.255C (-0.965)	2.725 – 3.99C (-0.988)	2.828 – 4.505C (-0.985)
	SDSB-2 + DMF		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	944.64 + 118.27C (0.998)	943.48 + 122.6C (1)	942.94 + 125.1C (0.997)
η (mPa s)	0.892 + 1.776C (0.994)	0.843 + 1.878C (0.991)	0.843 + 1.884C (0.996)
U (m s ⁻¹)	1452.2 + 401.53C (0.996)	1461.1 + 369.59C (0.998)	1467.5 + 348C (0.991)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	5.016 – 3.231C (-0.997)	4.963 – 3.019C (-0.998)	4.922 – 2.861C (-0.993)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	4.962 – 1.594C (-0.996)	4.66 – 1.394C (-1)	4.645 – 1.356C (-0.993)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	5.205 – 8.957C (-0.998)	5.135 – 8.495C (-0.997)	5.117 – 8.235C (-1)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	1.454 + 2.21C (0.993)	1.6 + 1.835C (0.954)	1.698 + 1.61C (0.976)

tion between ρ or η or U with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature is observed. The change in ρ and U with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature are not as appreciable as η because molecular motion is much more affected by solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions in the solutions^{19,20}. The increase in ρ or η or U with concentration of Schiff bases confirmed increase in cohesive forces because of strong molecular interactions, while decrease in ρ or η or U with temperature supported decrease in cohesive forces. The increase in temperature has two opposite effects namely structure formation and structure destruction. The structure forming tendency is mainly due to solute-solvent interaction, while destruction of structure formed previously is due to thermal fluctuations²¹. When thermal energy is greater than that of interaction energy, it causes destruction in structure formed previously. The density and viscosity of the medium, pressure, temperature, etc. affect the speed of sound. Strong molecular interactions resulted increase in viscosity, i.e. solvophilic behavior of both the Schiff bases.

In order to understand the effect of concentration, temperature, nature of solvents and solutes on the molecular interactions in solutions, various acoustical parameters such as specific acoustical impedance (Z), adiabatic compressibility (κ_a), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f), intermolecular free path length (L_f), classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_{Cl}$), and viscous relaxation time (τ) were determined by using ρ , η and U data according to standard equations reported in our earlier work²² and correlated with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature. The least square equations and correlation coefficients (γ) for selected parameters are included in Tables 3 and 4. The concentration and temperature dependence of acoustical parameters furnish valuable information about strength of molecular interactions occurring in the solutions. A good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration of Schiff bases at three temperatures is observed. Whenever nonlinear behaviors are observed polynomial correlations are performed.

It is observed that Z ($\gamma = 0.956-0.998$) increased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and decreased with temperature in CF and it is increased linearly with temperature in DMF. Adiabatic compressibility is de-

creased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and increased with temperature and it is decreased linearly with temperature in DMF. Similarly R_m ($\gamma = 0.999-1.000$) and b ($\gamma = 0.999-1.000$) both increased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases in both the systems but practically no temperature effect was observed. Free path length is decreased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and increased linearly with temperature in CF and it is decreased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature in DMF. Viscous relaxation time ($\gamma = 0.949-0.999$) and classical absorption coefficient ($\gamma = 0.921-0.989$) both increased linearly with concentration of Schiff bases and decreased with temperature. The increase or decrease of above mentioned parameters with concentration and temperature justified presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Adiabatic compressibility, internal pressure, free volume and free path length are influenced by concentration, temperature, nature of solvents and solutes. The decrease in π and increase in V_f and L_f indicated decrease in cohesive forces and vice versa. Viscous relaxation time and classical absorption coefficient are influenced by density, viscosity and temperature.

In order to understand molecular interactions in the solutions, solvation number (S_n) at different concentration of Schiff bases and at three different temperatures was determined. The plots of S_n against concentration of Schiff bases at three temperatures are presented in Figs. 1 and 2 from which it is clear that SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 confirmed structure forming tendency in both the solvent systems. The positive values of S_n for SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 indicated strong molecular interactions in the solutions. In case of SDSB-1 and SDSB-2, S_n increased nonlinearly with concentration of Schiff bases and decreased with temperature. The decrease in S_n above $0.060 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ indicated presence of powerful solute-solute interaction over solute-solvent interaction. Comparatively solvation phenomenon is greater in CF than DMF due to different polarity. The decrease in S_n with increasing temperature further supported destruction of structure formed previously as a result of thermal fluctuations.

Azomethine and hydroxyl groups are polar groups in Schiff bases. The C-Cl and lone pair of electrons and C=O groups of DMF are electronegative groups, while

Fig. 1. The plots of S_n against concentration of SDSB-1 at 303, 308 and 313 K in CF and DMF systems.

Fig. 2. The plots of S_n against concentration of SDSB-2 at 303, 308 and 313 K in CF and DMF systems.

methyl and C-H groups of DMF and C-H of CF are electropositive groups. The dipole-dipole interaction of opposite type results in structure formation and of same type results in destruction of the structure. Strong molecular interactions is expected in SDSB-1 as compared to SDSB-2 because azomethine and hydroxyl groups in SDSB-1 are relatively nearer than SDSB-2 and hence interact strongly with electronegative and electropositive parts of the solvents molecules. Strong interaction is more likely in DMF system and it is reflected in ρ , η and U data. In both the solvent systems SDSB-1 showed somewhat more viscosity than SDSB-2, while SDSB-2 solutions showed somewhat higher speed of sound and density. Because of molecular association apparent molecular weight and apparent molecular volume of the solute change in the solution and hence density of the solution also changed. Azomethine and hydroxyl groups of SDSB-1 have more tendencies to interact with solvent molecules. Thus SDSB-1 has more structure forming tendency in DMF than that of SDSB-2 and minimum in CF. Solute-solute interaction compete with solvent-solute interaction with increasing concentration of Schiff bases. Increasing solute-solute interaction causes destruction of structure formed as a consequence of solvent-solute interaction. Structure forming tendency of Schiff bases indicated that solvent-solute interaction is predominant over solute-solute interaction resulting in nonlinear behavior.

Conclusions

Various acoustical parameters of Schiff bases solutions were derived using density, viscosity and speed of sound at three different temperatures and interpreted in light of effect of concentration and nature of Schiff bases, nature of solvents and temperature. A good to excellent correlation between acoustical parameters with concentration of Schiff bases and temperature confirmed existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Both Schiff bases showed structure forming tendency.

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Gangani *et al.* : Speed of sound and associated acoustical parameters of Schiff base solutions *etc.*

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